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Critical Legal Appraisal of the Digital Personal Data Protection Act, 2023: Privacy Protection or State Control

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Abstract

In the digital era, data is often referred to as the new oil. The increasing reliance on technology for communication, governance, and commerce has raised profound concerns about how personal data is collected, stored, and used. The right to privacy, especially informational privacy, has come to the forefront of legal and policy debates. Following the landmark judgment in Justice K.S. Puttaswamy v. Union of India (2017), the Indian government introduced a series of bills culminating in the enactment of the Digital Personal Data Protection Act, 2023. This paper investigates whether the Act fulfills its promise to safeguard personal data in alignment with constitutional values or, alternatively, grants disproportionate powers to the State under the pretext of regulation.

Keywords Critical Legal, Data Protection, Privacy Protection.

Introduction

In the digital era, data is often referred to as the new oil. The increasing reliance on technology for communication, governance, and commerce has raised profound concerns about how personal data is collected, stored, and used. The right to privacy, especially informational privacy, has come to the forefront of legal and policy debates. Following the landmark judgment in Justice K.S. Puttaswamy v. Union of India (2017), the Indian government introduced a series of bills culminating in the enactment of the Digital Personal Data Protection Act, 2023. This paper investigates whether the Act fulfills its promise to safeguard personal data in alignment with constitutional values or, alternatively, grants disproportionate powers to the State under the pretext of regulation.

Objective of study

1. To examine the legal and doctrinal foundations of the Digital Personal Data Protection (DPDP) Act, 2023, in the context of the Indian Constitution and the right to privacy.
2. To analyze whether the DPDP Act aligns with constitutional standards or enables excessive state control over personal digital data.
3. To critically evaluate key provisions of the Act, including: Obligations of data fiduciaries, Rights of data principals, State exemptions under Section 17.
4. To assess the effectiveness and independence of institutional mechanisms like the Data Protection Board.
5. To evaluate the practical functioning of the consent-based data protection framework in India.
6. To conduct a comparative analysis between the DPDP Act and the European Union's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) to identify strengths and weaknesses of the Indian model.
7. To determine whether the DPDP Act adequately protects the right to privacy or risks undermining it through ambiguous and potentially overreaching provisions.

Review of Literature

Justice K.S. Puttaswamy v. Union of India (2017) marked a watershed moment, where a nine-judge bench unanimously upheld the right to privacy as a fundamental right under Article 21 of the Constitution. This case laid the constitutional foundation for data protection legislation in India.

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M.P. Sharma v. Satish Chandra (1954) and Kharak Singh v. State of U.P. (1963) had ruled against recognizing privacy as a fundamental right. However, these decisions were later overruled by Puttaswamy.

Gobind v. State of M.P. (1975), the court made early inroads by conditionally recognizing privacy, foreshadowing its later status as a full-fledged fundamental right.

Digital Personal Data Protection Act, 2023 (DPDP Act) is India's first comprehensive data protection law, aimed at safeguarding personal data and regulating its processing. It follows global norms while tailoring provisions to India's digital ecosystem.

European Union's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (2016) is a benchmark framework that has influenced data privacy laws worldwide, including India's DPDP Act. The GDPR emphasizes principles like consent, data minimization, and user rights, which are echoed in India's legislation.

Bhatia, G. (2019) In *The Transformative Constitution*, Bhatia examines how constitutional interpretation has evolved in India, especially in the realm of rights. He argues that the Constitution must be interpreted in a progressive, transformative manner to fulfill its egalitarian promises—an idea that underpins the judicial articulation of the right to privacy.

Sinha, A. (2023) This article explores the constitutional and legislative risks associated with the DPDP Act. It critically assesses gaps in the Act, particularly in terms of state surveillance and inadequate institutional safeguards, raising concerns about the balance between privacy and state power.

Sharma, R. (2023) Writing in the *Economic and Political Weekly*, Sharma provides a policy-focused critique of the DPDP Act. The article questions whether the Act is future-ready, pointing to weaknesses in enforcement, independence of the Data Protection Board, and exemptions for government agencies.

Main Text Right to Privacy: A Constitutional Perspective

The right to privacy in India has evolved gradually through judicial interpretation. Initially dismissed in *M.P. Sharma v. Satish Chandra (1954)* and *Kharak Singh v. State of U.P. (1962)*, the Supreme Court shifted its stance in cases such as *Gobind v. State of M.P. (1975)*, laying early groundwork for privacy as a derivative of Article 21. The landmark judgment in *Justice K.S. Puttaswamy v. Union of India (2017)* categorically declared privacy as a fundamental right, encompassing multiple dimensions—bodily, decisional, and informational privacy.

Importantly, the Court emphasized that any invasion of privacy must pass the three-pronged test: (i) legality, (ii) necessity and proportionality, and (iii) legitimate state interest. These principles serve as the constitutional benchmark against which any data protection law must be evaluated.

Overview of the Digital Personal Data Protection Act, 2023

The DPDP Act, 2023, is India's first comprehensive legal framework regulating the processing of digital personal data. Key features include:

1. **Data Principal and Data Fiduciary:** Individuals whose data is processed are "Data Principals," while entities processing the data are "Data Fiduciaries."
2. **Consent Framework:** Data processing is permitted only after obtaining the free, informed, specific, and unambiguous consent of the data principal.
3. **Rights of Individuals:** The Act provides rights such as the right to access information, correction and erasure of data, grievance redress, and the right to nominate.
4. **Obligations of Fiduciaries:** Fiduciaries must ensure data security, limit retention, and notify breaches.
5. **Data Protection Board:** A quasi-judicial body empowered to enforce the Act.
6. **Despite its progressive language, the Act includes provisions that raise serious concerns about state overreach and lack of accountability.**

Legal Critique of the DPDP Act, 2023

4.1 State Exemptions under Section 17

Perhaps the most controversial provision is Section 17, which allows the government to exempt any "instrumentality of the State" from complying with all or any provisions of the Act in the interest of national security, public order, or friendly relations with foreign states. This clause lacks specificity, transparency, and accountability, creating an

unfettered discretion for state surveillance—an affront to the proportionality doctrine laid down in Puttaswamy.

4.2 Consent Architecture

Although the Act mandates consent, it is arguably formalistic and does not require fiduciaries to explain consequences of consent denial or withdrawal. Moreover, for “deemed consent” under Section 7, processing is allowed in situations where it is not practically feasible to obtain consent—diluting the autonomy of data principals.

4.3 Role and Independence of the Data Protection Board

The Data Protection Board is envisaged as a regulator but is entirely appointed and controlled by the Central Government. Its independence is questionable, especially given that enforcement of penalties and adjudication of privacy violations will fall under its jurisdiction. In comparison, the EU’s Data Protection Authorities (DPAs) are functionally and financially independent.

4.4 Grievance Redress and Enforcement Gaps

While the Act provides a framework for grievance redress, it lacks judicial remedies akin to constitutional or civil litigation. There’s no clear route for constitutional challenge or effective appeal from the Board’s decision, which may impede access to justice.

Comparative Legal Insights: GDPR vs. DPDP

The EU’s General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) remains the global gold standard for data protection. A comparative analysis reveals:

Key Parameter	DPDP Act, 2023	GDPR (EU)
Consent Standard	Broad, allows deemed consent	Strict, informed, specific consent
Regulator Independence	Appointed by Central Govt	Independent Data Protection Authorities
Exemptions for State	Broad under Section 17	Narrow, strictly limited
Data Localization	Silent	Transfers allowed with safeguards
Right to be Forgotten	Recognized but weak enforcement	Strong and enforceable

While the GDPR is rights-centric, the DPDP Act appears compliance-focused with a tilt towards state facilitation over individual empowerment.

State Power vs. Individual Rights: Finding the Balance

The central challenge lies in striking a balance between legitimate state interests (security, governance, public order) and the individual’s right to privacy. While the state certainly needs access to certain data for governance, unchecked powers and vague exemptions run the risk of creating a surveillance state.

The absence of a surveillance regulation law, such as a revised Telegraph Act or updated IT rules, worsens the situation. The DPDP Act neither integrates with nor reforms existing surveillance laws—leading to legal fragmentation and uncertainty about its application vis-à-vis intelligence agencies.

Conclusion

The Digital Personal Data Protection Act, 2023 represents a long-awaited attempt to regulate personal data in India. While it incorporates foundational principles of data protection—like purpose limitation, consent, and accountability—it falls short in terms of constitutional safeguards, independent oversight, and individual rights enforcement. Key concerns include excessive state exemptions, lack of regulatory independence, and limited transparency.

Suggested Reforms:

1. Narrow and review Section 17 exemptions with clear judicial oversight.
2. Ensure functional independence of the Data Protection Board.
3. Strengthen data principal rights and include explicit rights such as data portability and impact assessments.
4. Integrate surveillance and data protection laws for a unified privacy framework.

India’s digital future must rest on a privacy-first approach that honors the Constitution, empowers individuals, and holds both public and private actors accountable.

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